

Implications of the COVID-19 application in the healthcare sector

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ABSTRACT

Since the beginning of the COVID-19 crisis, governments all over the world have been working on the development of COVID-19 applications. In this paper we investigate the digital transformation which follows from the use of the COVID-19 in the healthcare sector. We investigate this by looking at different parts of the digital transformation: business process integration, cybersecurity, and IT governance. After analyzing the pre and post COVID-19 situations, we conclude that several parts of the hospital's operations are affected by the COVID-19 application. The largest impact is on the diagnosis and performance of additional research. These processes are sped up by integrating data from the COVID19 app as input for their diagnostic analysis and additional research. It is expected that due to the crisis situation of COVID-19 the need of hospitals for reliable and timely information has increased. It is also expected that the medical professionals of hospitals recognize this need and have a greater demand for information. Because of this change in information needs, the IT groups need to finetune their services to the needs of the medical professionals. Finally, we discuss how the COVID-19 application affects risks management in hospitals. We conclude that there are several data risks when using the app. Using a number of controls, we try to limit these data risks. Some controls decrease the impact of a risk, others minimize the likelihood of it.

Keywords

COVID-19, COVID-19 application, corona, SARS-CoV-2, crisis, healthcare, hospital, business process integration, IT governance, cybersecurity, risk management

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of the COVID-19 crisis, governments all over the world have been working on the development of COVID-19 applications. The main goal of these applications is to warn people

when they have had contact with someone who tested positive for the new COVID-19 virus. One of the first countries to develop this application was Australia (Abbas and Michael, 2020). The app was first released on 26 April 2020. Since then, several other countries have followed, among which are England and Wales (O'Dowd, 2020). The first lessons learned from Australia and Singapore from these tracing applications are already available (Abbas and Michael, 2020).

The Dutch government has released their first COVID-19 application on 10 October 2020. Research suggests that the adoption rate for a secure and privacy-respecting application will be as high as 64% in the Netherlands (Jonker, Veldwijk, Goossens, Bour, and Rutten-Van Mólken, 2020). When the application is used by a representative percentage of the population, the application will generate a large amount of data. This data could possibly be used to generate predictions about the progress of the virus for the healthcare industry. Hospitals in the Netherlands could benefit greatly from these predictions. This paper will therefore focus on the way the COVID-19 application data can influence how hospitals respond during a crisis. This is done with a 'what if' research, pretending that hospitals in the Netherlands have access to the data generated by the COVID-19 app. This research has not been conducted before in the Netherlands, it is however an important topic to research, because the outcomes can be used to support hospitals.

2. RESEARCH

In the second chapter, the research objective and approach are described. Several research questions are defined, and the methods that are used are described.

2.1 Objective

The objective of this research is to find knowledge about data influencing the way hospitals respond in crisis situations. First, the focus will be on how the COVID-19 application affects key IT

governance aspects in hospitals, for example, what changes the usage of the application entails in decision making. Second, the changes in the key internal processes of hospitals by COVID-19 are discussed, together with the usage of data uit the COVID-19 application. Third, it is analyzed how the COVID-19 application affects risk management in hospitals. Finally, an historical security incident in the health sector is analyzed for the cybersecurity part of this paper.

2.2 Approach

To achieve the objectives and find new knowledge, a research question is defined:

'How does data input influence the way hospitals respond to crisis situations?'

We want to answer this question by performing a case analysis from multiple different perspectives as defined in the objective. Based on these perspectives, sub questions are defined:

- How does the COVID-19 application affect key IT governance aspects in hospitals?
- How does the COVID-19 application affect the operations (key internal processes) of hospitals?
- How does the COVID-19 application affect risk management in hospitals?

In addition to this part of the research, an additional cybersecurity part has been added wherein a historical security incident has been analyzed.

The data of this research is collected by performing a literature review, combining academic articles with newspaper articles for the newest COVID-19 developments and the historical cybersecurity incident. Since the first part of this research focuses on hospitals as a specific part of the healthcare sector, data will additionally be collected from the website of the hospitals based on representativeness and information availability.

3. SECTOR

The sector this research is in, is 'Health & Medical', also known by the healthcare industry. This sector provides products and services to treat patients. The sector can be divided in several components, for example, manufacturing drugs, providing medical equipment, and providing health care facilities (Chappelow, 2020). For this research paper, the focus will be on sub industry hospitals, in combination with the influence of COVID-19 and the COVID-19 application.

Characteristics

According to an industry report of Statista (2020), the estimated revenue of the healthcare

industry was US\$2,487.7 billion in just the United States. Nearly half of this revenue was generated by the hospital sub industry for the U.S. This example shows the worldwide volume of the sector. The sector can be related to almost every other sector, for example, the Production & Manufacturing sector (producing health machines) and the Education & Career sector (train medical employees).

Key developments

The COVID-19 crisis draws attention to the already overburdened health systems in many countries and to the demand for recruiting, deploying, retaining, and protecting a sufficient number of well-trained, supported, and motivated health workers. It strongly emphasizes the need for sustainable investment in health systems, including health workers, and decent working conditions, training, and equipment, especially concerning personal protective equipment and occupational safety. Social communication is essential for building resilient health systems and therefore plays a vital role in both crisis response and in building a future prepared for health emergencies (Kangqi Ng, Beng Hoon Poon, 2020)

Using information from COVID-19 application

Worldwide, several COVID-19 applications are developed. As described above, this research will focus on the effect of the usage of this application on hospitals. According to Javaid, Haleem, Vaishya, Bahl, Suman, and Vaish (2020), several techniques can help in COVID-19 outbreaks. For example, Artificial Intelligence can help to predict outbreaks, and Big Data can be used for analysing and forecasting the impact of the virus. A research by Whitelaw, Mamas, Topo l, and Van Spall (2020) shows the digital technology initiatives that are used in COVID-19 applications. For example, tracking and contact tracing functionalities are used (Whitelaw et al., 2020). The information that is generated by the software applications can be used for many things. An example of using COVID-19 data is China, by initiating health checks for airline travellers. These checks are based on the integration of data from immigration records with China's national health insurance database, and collected actual COVID-19 data (Whitelaw et al., 2020).

4. ANALYSIS

Within this chapter, the research questions will be answered as defined in chapter 2.

4.1 IT Governance

In this section, the impact of the COVID-19 application on the key IT governance aspects in hospitals will be discussed. First, the situation before

COVID-19 is explained. Second, the situation after COVID-19 will be discussed.

AS-IS

In a study by (Xue, Liang, & Boulton, 2008), six different hospitals are examined in their IT investment process. In this investigation, the researchers conclude that the approval of decision making in hospitals is primarily performed by the top management (business monarchy). This is supported by table 1 below, which states that at all of 34 IT investment decisions the approval was done by the top management. If we translate this to the Ross & Weill Governance Matrix, this would indicate that all investment decisions are made by the business monarchy. In table 1, initiation can be seen as the initiation of the investment process. In table 1, 30 of the 34 initiations were done by the top management. The top management thus recognized a need for certain investments. Then, the development of this investment process was mainly done by IT professionals (26 of 30). The IT professionals developed the initial ideas of the top management to ensure top management would make the correct decision. At the end of the investment process, top management decides whether the investment, which was initiated by the top management and developed by the IT professionals, is made. Reflecting on the study from Xue et al. (2008) we compared this to the findings of a study by Weill (2004). Weill describes a scenario very similar to the findings of Xue et al. (2008). He describes a scenario in which a centralized organization is mainly governed by decisions of the business monarchies. Additionally, he describes in which situations this centralized scenario could be applicable: “More centralized approaches are typically used in firms with single business units or where profitability or cost control is a predominant issue” (Weill, 2004, p. 15). Since the main healthcare operations of hospitals often operate as a single business unit (Rydenfält, Larsson, & Odenrick, 2017), this corresponds with the findings of the study by Xue et al. (2008).

Table 1: IT governance archetypes grouped by IT investment level.(Xue et al. (2008))

After comparing the findings of the case studies in the hospitals by Xue et al. (2008) with the

theories provided by Weill (2004), we designed the IT governance matrix, as described in a study by Ross & Weill (2004). In this matrix, depicted in table 2, we show how different organizational parts give input and decide on different IT decision areas. For each decision, except for the business application needs, we propose that the business monarchy decides. This follows from the centralized set-up of the hospital and the findings of the study by Xue et al. (2008) as described earlier in this section. For the business application needs, we look at the theory provided by Weill (2004) who states that centralized organizations often make business application needs on a federal level. Next, the input for each decision is delivered by the business monarchy, IT monarchy, and IT duopoly. This also follows from the findings of the case studies performed by Xue et al. (2008). This means that the input for the different decision areas is delivered by individual or groups of business executives (1), individual or groups of IT executives (2), and/or IT executives and one other group, such as the CEO or BU leaders (3).

Governance Archetype	Decision Domain									
	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Business Monarchy	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x
IT Monarchy	x		x		x		x		x	
Feudal										
Federal								x		
Duopoly	x		x		x		x		x	
Anarchy										

Table 2: AS IS

TO-BE

In the sections above, the As-Is situation was described. In the next sections, the IT governance structure that would best satisfy the needs of hospitals as they emerge from the COVID-19 disruption, and as they are going to use a COVID-19 application.

It is expected that due to the crisis situation of COVID-19 the need of hospitals for reliable and timely information has increased. It is also expected that the medical professionals of hospitals recognize this need and have a greater demand for information. Because of this change information needs, the IT groups need to finetune their services to the needs of the medical professionals. The COVID-19 application offers hospitals the opportunity to gain local insight into COVID-19. This requires more flexibility and faster development of IT services. In addition, this shift influences the inputs into the decisions. Medical professionals (anarchy) want to deliver their input into IT decisions because this will also heavily impact their work. The changes in the IT governance decision-making process are

visualized in the IT governance matrix, as described in the study by Ross & Weill (2004). This matrix is stated in table 3 below.

		Decision Domain										
		IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment		
		Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	
Governance Archetype	Business Monarchy	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
	IT Monarchy	x		x		x		x			x	
	Feudal											
	Federal	x		x		x		x	x		x	
	Duopoly	x		x		x		x			x	
	Anarchy											

Table 3: TO BE

4.2 Business Process Integration

In this section, the second sub-question is discussed. The focus will be on how the COVID-19 application affects the key internal process of providing care in hospitals. First, the situation before COVID-19 is discussed. Several sources are used to create one BPMN-model that can be generalized for the hospital sector. Second, the process changes that COVID-19 entails are discussed.

4.2.1 Pre COVID-19 analysis

Determine care needs

The first step of the process consists of determining the patient's care needs. Once the care needs have been determined, a physical appointment will be made.

Diagnosis

The next step in diagnosing the patient. This step starts with preparing the physical contact. After that, the patient is received in the hospital and additional information will be collected. The additional information is assessed and a diagnosis is made based on that (Rolón, Aguilar, Garcia, Ruiz, Piattini, & Calahorra, 2008).

Form treatment plan

Based on the diagnosis a patient receives a treatment plan. In this step, the diagnosis is assessed and a treatment plan is drawn up. The treatment plan specifies the care that the patient needs (Rolón et al., 2008).

Treat

Based on the treatment plan and when applicable, a patient receives treatment. The treatment will first be prepared and thereafter be carried out. The specific treatment is personalized for each patient and may consist of, for example, therapy or surgery. When the treatment is done, it will be evaluated.

Advise

In addition to a specific treatment, a patient can also receive advice from specialists. First, the specific request is determined and assessed. Based on this information, the patient will receive personalized advice (Vercruyse, 2009).

Perform additional research

Besides the diagnosis, treatment plan, and treatment, additional research can be performed. Also in this process step, the specific research content is personalized per patient. Generally, first of all, the specific research question is discussed. Then, the research is planned and prepared. After that, the actual research is going to be performed. When the results are gathered, specialists will assess them and report back to the involved parties, e.g. the patient (Müller, Rogge-Solti, 2011).

Transfer

The last step in the process is transferring the patient. There are a few options within this process step. The patient could be transferred to another care agency (e.g. physiotherapist or nursing home) or the patient can be released from the hospital (Müller, Rogge-Solti, 2011).

Figure 1

4.2.2 During and after COVID-19

The COVID-19 application affects multiple process steps, additionally, it creates two extra process steps that did not exist prior to the COVID-19 outbreak.

Diagnose

Based on a research by Rolón et al. (2008), we assume steps in the diagnosis process include activities such as the preparation of contact, the actual contact with the patient, acquiring additional information, the assessment of the information gathered by the additional research, and the actual diagnosis. The additional data gathered by the COVID-19 application, as described below in the 'perform additional research' section, heavily affects the diagnosis of a patient. Specifically, it affects the acquiring of additional data, since this can now be done much quicker with the help of the COVID-19 application. Furthermore, the assessment of the information is affected, since the

COVID-19 application contains medical data from a relatively trustworthy source (the government). The actual diagnosis clearly does not change, a patient can either have the COVID-19 virus or not. However, the speed of the entire diagnosis process is affected. Due to the additional information already gathered by the app, healthcare professionals obtain a good indication that the patient could possibly have the COVID-19 virus. Therefore, they can purposefully test the patient on the COVID-19 virus, which speeds up the process.

The preparation of contact and the actual contact with the patient most likely will not differ from COVID-19 patients that are not using the app.

Perform additional research

When additional research is performed, the hospital staff can request information about the patient from the COVID-19 application. The application collects data about the patients contacts and whereabouts. This could help determine if the patient has a higher risk of COVID-19. If the patient has a higher risk the hospital can decide to keep the patient in isolation until the result of the COVID-19 test is known.

Receive COVID-19 application patient data

The hospital sends a request for information to the COVID-19 application. When this request is approved, the hospital receives patient data from the application. This data includes a risk profile for the patient and the contacts he or she has had in the past 10 days.

Send COVID-19 diagnosis to government or application

If a patient gets tested positive for the COVID-19 virus, the hospital has to inform the government or application about the positive test. The application can then warn people that have been in close contact with the patient in the past 10 days.

4.2.3 Conclusion

After analyzing the pre and post COVID-19 situations, we conclude that several parts of the hospital's operations are affected by the COVID-19 application. The largest impact is on the diagnosis and performance of additional research. These processes are sped up by utilizing data from the COVID-19 app as input for their diagnostic analysis and additional research. Additionally, two extra process steps are created for the input and output of the COVID-19 application data. In order to include this data in the process, the data will have to be integrated into the hospital's databases. A link between the hospital's systems and the COVID-19 application could for example be established with the use of middleware software. In this research, we

mainly focussed on the implications of the COVID-19 application on the core hospital process, which is to provide care to any new patients. However, the detailed implications for systems and databases is not examined further and will be part of our recommendations for future research in this field.

4.3 Cybersecurity and risk management

In this third analysis, we will discuss how the COVID-19 application affects risk management in hospitals. By using the COVID-19 application, additional risks can be identified. These risks are explained below and made visible in a risk matrix. In conclusion, relevant measures are defined. In this analysis, we examine not only the COVID-19 application, but rather the entire socio-technical system. Meaning that we additionally examine vulnerabilities on the user side of the system, instead of only technical aspects that could result into risks.

Identified vulnerabilities and risks:

1. The anonymized user-data within the app can be de-anonymized (e.g. device information and IP-address) (Bock, Kühne, Mühlhoff, R., Ost, Pohle, & Rehak, 2020)
2. Commercial tracking by e.g. billboards and shopping malls that are already equipped with BT-based tracking infrastructure (Bock, et al., 2020).
3. Centralized data storage can cause data misuse (by e.g. the government) (Bock, et al., 2020).
4. Large scale bluetooth hacking, e.g. by automated break-ins into the devices of any users at a location where the attacker and the target are in close proximity for a short time (Bock, et al., 2020).
5. Less experienced people will be persuaded to install malware via fake emails / messages. This can result in them being robbed.
6. Cyber attacks that generate fake contacts with the potential of significantly affecting the accuracy and integrity of an app-based contact tracing system.
7. Lost smartphones or flawed bluetooth sensors can result in users being wrongly isolated, with considerable economic and social consequences to those affected (Bock, et al., 2020).
8. Personal data is processed by Google and Apple, it is however unclear which data they can use and how this data is

adequately protected (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, 2020).

- Users of the application can voluntarily indicate in the application whether they tested positive for COVID-19. This could lead to false positives/negatives (CoronaMelder, 2020).

Figure 2: Risk matrix before controls

Identified controls:

- Use encryption to protect anonymized data and prevent it from being de-anonymized.
- Add an anti-tracking module to the COVID-19 application.
- Use (social) media (also television to target older people) for a national awareness campaign and to emphasize the importance of data integrity in the app.
- Employ a data protection officer, who's main task is to identify and prevent hacks and coordinate app security improvements.
- Program a functionality in the COVID-19 app to check the Bluetooth-sensor and a functionality to block the application when smartphones are lost.
- The government has to make clear agreements with Google and Apple stating which data can and cannot be processed by Google and Apple.
- The positive test indication in the application should be validated by the GGD or the institute responsible for the testing.

If the controls are implemented, the impact and/or probability of the risk can change. We expect the new risk matrix to look as follows:

Figure 3: Risk matrix after controls

Conclusion

Concluding, several controls, such as the employment of a data protection officer, are

applicable to multiple risks. These combinations are shown in table 1 in Appendix A. Some controls decrease the impact of a risk, others minimize the likelihood of it. As shown in figure 3 above, most changes happen in risks numbers nine and five. This, for example, because the impact of a test result validation by the GGD before the result can be entered into the app, will minimize the likelihood that this risk will occur.

4.4 Term paper cybersecurity and risk management

In addition to section 4.3, where we discussed how the COVID-19 application affects risk management in hospitals, an security incident has been researched.

This report describes a cyber incident at the company American Medical Collection Agency (AMCA). AMCA is a provider of billing services for the US healthcare sector. It was founded in 1977. Searching on Google for 'hospital data breaches' gives a lot of results about recent security incidents. According to Davis (2020), 41.4 million patient records were breached in 2019, wherein 2018, 15 million records were stolen.

In 2018, the personal data of over 20 million patients of American laboratories were exposed by a data breach. The data breach was discovered after a period of eight months. The exposed data included inter alia names, home addresses, phone numbers, dates of birth, and bank account information. Of the 20 million people affected by the data breach, only 200,000 were contacted by AMCA. Thus, more than 60 days after the healthcare data breach at AMCA was discovered, only a tiny percentage of medical healthcare patients had been told about it.

In the next section, the conclusion of this security report is described. In the sections after the conclusion, these statements are justified. First, the time-line of the security incident is explained. Second, a risk analysis is written down. Finally, some recommendations are given.

Conclusions

Concluding, the AMCA case had a large impact due to a combination of several factors. Namely, AMCA's insufficient monitoring of unauthorized access to data led to a late discovery of the breach and additionally AMCA's late response after discovering the breach increased the impact of it. Various controls, such as DNS monitoring, database structure controls, and the use of transparency between different parties could have decreased the likelihood and/or impact of this large data breach. To prevent similar data breaches in the future, we propose several recommendations. These recommendations include multiple types of access

control, audits, response strategies, data anonymization and the transparency of data and security measures.

Time-line of the security incident

On August 1 2018, hackers started accessing the healthcare data of AMCA. The hackers were able to access private information, for example, names, date of birth, addresses, payment card information, and bank account information (Lindsey, 2019). The hack has gone unnoticed until February 2019. At the end of this month, analysts of Gemini Advisory identified a database that had been posted on the dark web. Since the specific personal data in the database was rarely sold, the analysts suspected a hack in an online portal. Initially, the Gemini researchers identified around 8,000 victims. However, additional research showed at least 200,000 victims and exposed the hack started in August. With this information, Gemini contacted AMCA. However, the company did not respond. Thereafter, Gemini informed federal law enforcement to inform them about the data breach (DataBreaches.net, 2019). After being confronted with the hack, AMCA officially admitted the security incident on March 30, 2019. AMCA, after being compromised, initially claimed that the data of 200,000 patiënt was stolen. However, the U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) researched the incident and found more than 20 million victims (Cimpanu, 2019).

According to the HIPAA Act, companies have to notify their patients within 60 days after a healthcare data breach discovery. In addition to the data breach being undiscovered for over eight months, AMCA waited for weeks or months before alerting their customers. According to Lindsey (2019), just 200,000 of the 20 million victims have been contacted by AMCA in the weeks after the breach. In conclusion, more than 60 days after the breach, just a small percentage of the involved healthcare patients have been informed.

As a result of the data breach, several legal actions were set in motion in several different states. On June 17, the parent company of AMCA, Retrieval-Masters Creditors Bureau, filed for bankruptcy due to the data breach (Garrity, 2019).

Figure 4: Time-line of the security incident

Risk Analysis

Confidentiality

1. Information stolen from external parties, such as patients of laboratories, can result in personal data being sold on the dark web or used by criminals. The types of information include for example names, phone numbers, and balance information (Whitakker, 2019).
2. Information stolen from direct clients of AMCA, such as credit card or banking information, can be used to drain money from bank accounts of clients of AMCA (Whittaker, 2019), (Databreaches.net, 2019).
3. Insufficient monitoring of access to data, which can lead to a data breach being undetected for a long period of time, such as almost a year in the case of AMCA (Whitakker, 2019).
4. Late reporting of discovered data breaches can lead to hackers using the data for fraudulent purposes, such as selling payment card data on the dark web (Lindsey, 2019). In the case of AMCA, the time before notification was in some cases even months, which is longer than the 60 days stated in the HIPAA Act (Office for Civil Rights (2013).

Integrity

5. If the company where the data breach occurred is not transparent about it, it may be impossible for the external parties to verify the accuracy of the data breach information they receive from the company (Databreaches.net, 2019).

Availability

6. If the company where the data breach occurred is not able to provide its clients with the information on which data was stolen in the breach, this can lead to the client not being able to warn the right customers about the data breach. In the case of AMCA, AMCA could not provide CPL with requested information about the data breach (Whitakker, 2019).

Controls

Looking at the different risks mentioned above, we identify the following possible controls that were applied in the AMCA case.

1. Organizations frequently monitor the Domain Name System (DNS) for evidence of data theft or unauthorized activity (Davis, 2019).
2. Organizations store sensitive data, such as medical records and financial records, in separate database tables or systems. By for example using a third table containing patient data, the tables can be linked. But without having access to all tables, the data can't be linked to patients. (Davis, 2019)
3. The protection of data should be a collective effort and responsibility of all companies involved in the supply chain. Companies should evaluate their vendors cyber security measures before signing a contract. When risk management and cybersecurity becomes a collaborative process, and is included in the contract, this could result in more transparency and accountability (Davis, 2019).

Risks versus controls

Comparing these controls to the risks identified earlier, the likelihood of confidentiality issues, such as the personal information stolen from external parties, could be minimized by implementing the correct database structure as discussed in control number two. The impact of such confidentiality issues could be reduced by frequently monitoring the DNS for unauthorized activity, as described in control number one. Additionally the impact of confidentiality risks could be reduced further by promoting transparency of security measures and controls of vendors. If this transparency would have been applied correctly in the case of AMCA, the data breach was likely found much sooner. This

transparency could also be used to solve integrity, accuracy, and availability issues, as described in risk number five. This since transparency between the vendor and client will allow easier access to data, according to rules and regulations.

Recommendations

Based on the AMCA case, some lessons learned can be defined. In this section, some recommendations are defined to prevent and control this kind of security incident.

Data anonymization has been defined as a "process by which personal data is irreversibly altered in such a way that a data subject can no longer be identified directly or indirectly, either by the data controller alone or in collaboration with any other party" according to ISO 25237:2017. Data anonymization may enable the transfer of information across a boundary, such as between two departments within an agency or between two agencies, while reducing the risk of unintended disclosure, and in certain environments in a manner that enables evaluation and analytics post-anonymization

At a very basic level, access control is a means of controlling who enters a location and when. The person entering may be an employee, a contractor or a visitor etc. The location they are entering may be, for example, a site, a building, a room or a cabinet. It is important to determine how to integrate the right level of secure access to the people who need it. Below are a number of recommendations for effective and efficient access control:

- Evaluate Your Access Control System Features
- Determine your access levels
- Audit who has access
- Update your technology
- Perform Periodic Access Control Systems Testing

One of the biggest issues in the AMCA case was about the company not (or not in time) informing the victims of the data breach. According to the HIPAA Act, the AMCA should have informed their patients within 60 days. However, the company failed and several legal actions were started because of this negligence. Recommended to every company is to inform their affected customers within the time-frame that is specified in the relevant legislation. In addition, organizations should take notifications of external parties about possible data breaches or other security incidents seriously. In the AMCA case, the company ignored the reports about the data breach of the Gemini researchers. In this case, the data breach was done months before its discovery.

However, in other cases, taking notifications of (possible) incidents very seriously, could prevent the incident happening, or could limit the damage. In conclusion, organisations should set up their governance to deal with this kind of notification.

In the AMCA case, a lot of mistakes could have been avoided if the vendor and client relationship would have been better. The clients in this case were the labs that outsourced the payment service to AMCA. Before sharing personal customer data with AMCA, they should have made sure AMCA was protecting this data accurately instead of just relying on AMCA. By investing in the vendor-client relationship, organizations can influence the information they are receiving and overlook the security measures the service provider is taking to protect the data. They can also intervene if they think measures are not sufficient. This collaboration creates more transparency and responsibility within the supply chain. As digital transformation is growing, risk management and cybersecurity will become more important. It therefore is crucial to embed both contractually in the vendor-client relationship (Davis, 2019).

5. DISCUSSION

Comparing our findings of the different types of digital transformations of the COVID-19 application, we identify several short- and long term implications for the healthcare sector. First of all, hospitals can expect changes in their diagnosis process. This process in specific is heavily affected, due to the possibilities of data integration between hospitals' data systems and the COVID-19 application. Subsequently, the process of providing care to patients can be sped up by utilizing this data integration in the diagnosis process. Secondly, in accordance with this change in data integration for hospitals, we expect that due to the COVID-19 crisis health care professionals have an increased need for timely and reliable information. To supply this need, IT governance becomes increasingly important to identify and decide on the correct business (healthcare professional) requirements for IT solutions. In terms of IT governance archetypes, an increase in the involvement of medical professionals in IT decisions will lead to a more federal decision-making system. The increased importance of the information of the COVID-19 application additionally places extra importance on the integrity of this data. One important risk here could be the fact that users of the COVID-19 application can voluntarily insert their COVID-19 test results into the application. This means that users can falsely indicate that they have the COVID-19 virus. To greatly reduce the likelihood of this risk, we identify a control that includes a verification of each test result that is entered into the COVID-19 application

by the GGD.

6. CONCLUSION

After analyzing the pre and post COVID-19 situations, we conclude that several parts of the hospital's operations are affected by the COVID-19 application. The largest impact is on the diagnosis and performance of additional research. These processes are sped up by utilizing data from the COVID-19 app as input for their diagnostic analysis and additional research.

It is expected that due to the crisis situation of COVID-19 the need of hospitals for reliable and timely information has increased. It is also expected that the medical professionals of hospitals recognize this need and have a greater demand for information. Because of this change information needs, the IT groups need to finetune their services to the needs of the medical professionals. The COVID-19 application offers hospitals the opportunity to gain local insight into COVID-19.

Finally, we discussed how the COVID-19 application affects risks management in hospitals. We concluded that there are a lot of data risks when using the app. Using a number of controls, we have tried to limit these data risks. Some controls decrease the impact of a risk, others minimize the likelihood of it.

Through this research we have learned a lot about digital transformation. However, the Covid-19 is a new phenomenon and it is still going on. This does not make it easy to draw specific and clear conclusions. The digital transformation as a whole is being deployed at a rapid pace while there are still many uncertainties. Because of these uncertainties there are some shortcomings in this research. So, when covid-19 is overcome, further research will be needed to reach even better insights in the digital transformation.

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9. APPENDIX

Appendix A: Risk versus controls

Risks	Applicable controls
1. The anonymized user-data within the app can be de-anonymized (e.g. device information and IP-address) (Bock, Kühne, Mühlhoff, R., Ost, Pohle, & Rehak, 2020)	1, 4
2. Commercial tracking by e.g. billboards and shopping malls that are already equipped with BT-based tracking infrastructure (Bock, et al., 2020).	1, 2, 4
3. Centralized data storage can cause data misuse (by e.g. the government) (Bock, et al., 2020).	1
4. Large scale bluetooth hacking, e.g. by automated break-ins into the devices of any users at a location where the attacker and the target are in close proximity for a short time (Bock, et al., 2020).	2, 4
5. Less experienced people will be persuaded to install malware via fake emails / messages. This can result in them being robbed.	3
6. Cyber attacks that generate fake contacts with the potential of significantly affecting the accuracy and integrity of an app-based contact tracing system.	4
7. Lost smartphones or flawed bluetooth sensors can result in users being wrongly isolated, with considerable economic and social consequences to those affected (Bock, et al., 2020).	5
8. Personal data is processed by Google and Apple, it is however unclear which data they can use and how this data is adequately protected (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens, 2020).	6
9. Users of the application can voluntarily indicate in the application whether they tested positive for COVID-19. This could lead to false positives/negatives (CoronaMelder, 2020).	3, 7

Table 1: Risk versus controls